

NFDI4Objects

Research Data Infrastructure
for the Material Remains of
Human History

LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM
FÜR ARCHÄOLOGIE

Taming Time: Using Correspondence Analysis to handle relative chronologies as graphs

EAA 2024 - Persisting with Change

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Session: Applying Archaeological Research Software Engineering as Little Minions

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Dated Sites in Archaeology

Do they exist?

Carlo Sanquirico (active 1820s–1830s) after Alessandro Sanquirico (1777–1849),
Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons

Jon Hawke,
via <https://twitter.com/HawkeJon/status/1402930033149321217>

In the 1st Century AD, there are very few verifiable *absolute dated* sites: e.g., *Pompei* and *Inchtuthil*, of which ancient authors indicated their dates.

Matthias Süßen, CC BY-SA 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

left: British Museum, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, via <https://www.britishmuseum.org/collection/image/1613222977>
right: Jacob More, CC BY-NC, via <https://www.nationalgalleries.org/art-and-artists/5205>

The *AD 79* catastrophe of *Pompeii* was reported to the senate by the son of *Plinius the Older* (who died there).

Coins < AD 87

Münzkabinett der Staatlichen Museen, Berlin, Public Domain Mark 1.0, Objektnummer 18232046. Aufnahme durch Dirk Sonnenwald, via <https://ikmk.smb.museum/object?id=18232046>

Tacitus

left: Pe-Jo, Public domain, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)
right: Tacitus, Public domain, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

At *Inchtuthil*, the coins series stop at AD 87 and the ancient author *Tacitus* reports the military campaign AD 83-87.

Phil Champion / Hadrian's wall at Cuddy's Crag and Housesteads Crag CC BY-SA 2.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Hadrian's Wall was built at the some time (3rd consulate?) after the start of his reign AD 117.

Samian Research ID	22341	Decoration Nr	0000000	OCK Vessel Nr	
Tradition	Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian				
Kilnsite	La Graufesenque				
Potter	Aquitanus (About)	OCK Potter Nr			
Die	11c ³⁹ (Graph Die Variety)	Special Reading	AQVITANI	Die position	Base inside
Frame No	0 info	Simple Reading		Reading Direction	Pro
Date	AD 40-65				
Form	(form variety)	Form attribute		Slip colour	
Site	Strasbourg? (7.750000, 48.583328) =Pleaden	Findspot		Findspot character	
	(Site statistics)				
Repository site					
Repository		Museum Inv. No		Excavation Nr	27359?
Amount	1				
Bibliography					
Comment					

Contrary to the reality, *potter dates* are frequently given dates like *from - to*, suggesting a dating certainty which is actually only a probability.

However, most Roman 1st Century AD dated sites are usually dated by Samian potters' stamps, which occur on other assumed dated sites, which are dated by Samian potters' stamps, thus potentially resulting in a circulus vitiosus.

A methodological way out of this dilemma is possible, when we enhance the assumed external dating evidence and go back to the factual occurrences and overlaps in the data from the suspected dated sites, since only these data are free of any temporal interpretations.

FAIR and Linked Open Data

How to implement these principles in Open Science?

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Dr. Heidi Seibold, CC BY 4.0, via 10.5281/zenodo.8070860

DFG, CC BY, via dfg.de and <https://youtu.be/uJ01g9m8uE4>

In Germany, the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) will help to establish sustainable structures and to create reproducible FAIRification processes.

image via ontotext.com

One standard applied within the NFDI is the Resource Description Framework (RDF).

Florian Thiery / LEIZA, [CC BY 4.0](#), via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

Florian Thiery, [CC BY 4.0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

**RDF's main concept are Triples.
The LOD Principles interlink RDF structures ...**

Florian Thiery / LEIZA, based on lod-cloud.net, CC BY 4.0

... to create a growing **Linked Open Data Cloud** ...

images by solidproject.org

image by iowacomputergurus.com

... using also technologies such as Solid Pods.

Data & Methods

Samian Research Database Correspondence Analysis

LEIZA / Samian Research

Allard Mees, CC BY 4.0

The online relational database Samian Research contains a quarter of a million finds of potters' stamps which are found throughout the Western Roman Empire.

Madsen (1988), Fig. 11

Following the horseshoe paradigm, a CA result may provide a measure of (possible chronological) overlap. It is important to note that a CA does not comprise any pre-known dating information.

	timeinterval	emperor	years
1	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Vitellius	1
2	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Galba	1
3	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Otho	1
4	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Vespasian	10
5	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Titus	2
6	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Domitian	15
7	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Nerva	2
8	fruehkaiserzeitlich	Trajan	19
9	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Vitellius	1
10	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Galba	1
11	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Otho	1
12	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Vespasian	10
13	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Titus	2
14	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Domitian	15
15	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Nerva	2
16	2ndHalfFirstCentury	Trajan	2
17	Usurpator	Galba	1
18	Usurpator	Otho	1
19	Usurpator	Vitellius	1
20	Usurpator	Vespasian	1
21	DomitianConsulate2	Domitian	1

image via [10.5281/zenodo.1410516](https://zenodo.org/record/1410516)

**CA - Method Test of Roman Emperors
and reigning years showing a horseshoe parabola.**

Use Case I: Province Britannia

CA to colourful maps & RDF graphs

TiGeR FAIRification Research Tool

Dienste

Korrespondenzanalyse
Seriation

csv-convert-Tool

Visualisierung von
Keramik

Über diese Webseite
Hilfe
Referenzen

Bitte wählen Sie Ihre
Sprache

Kontakt:
adp(at)rgzm.de

Letzte Änderung:
2018-10-08

Korrespondenzanalyse

Einstellungen zum Lesen der Daten

Feldtrenner: Texttrenner: Kopfzeile vorhanden Ja Nein

Type und Unit vertauschen Ja Nein minimale Anzahl für Types minimale Anzahl für Units

Farbkodierung:

- Dateinhalt
- Überschriften
- Datensätze zur Verwendung
- wegen Minimalbedingungen verworfene Datensätze
- Nicht numerischer Wert bei Auftreten

Anzahl aller Einträge: 1835
Anzahl verbleibender Einträge: 1702
Anzahl verbleibender Types: 83
Anzahl verbleibender Units: 202
Minimum sind jeweils 3

Zeilennummer	Daten aus Datei	Daten mit angewandten Einstellungen		
1	Alcester,Dontio;2	Alcester	Dontio	2
2	Alcester,lullinus i;2	Alcester	lullinus i	2
3	Alcester,Modestus i;3	Alcester	Modestus i	3
4	Alcester,Passenus (Passienus);5	Alcester	Passenus (Passienus)	5
5	Alcester,Primus iii;3	Alcester	Primus iii	3
6	Alcester,Logirinus;3	Alcester	Logirinus	3

LEIZA-ADP: Low threshold Correspondence Analyses
<https://www.rgzm.de/adp>

Britannia

Alcester;Dontio;2
Alcester;lullinus i;2
Alcester;Modestus i;3
Alcester;Passenus (Passienus);5
Alcester;Primus iii;3
Alcester;Logirinus;3
Alchester;Licinus;2
Alchester;Patricius i;2
Alchester;L. Cosius Virilis;2
Arlesey;Mont- Cres- (Montius Cres);2
Arlesey;Passenus (Passienus);2
Arlesey;Rutaenus;2
Arlesey;Felix i;2
Ashwell;Germanus i;3
Baginton;Murranus i;2
Baginton;Niger ii;5
Baginton;Passenus (Passienus);5
Baginton;Felix i;3
Baginton;Primus iii;2
Baldock;Germanus i;2
Baldock;Carbo;2
.....

Phil Champion / Hadrian's wall at Cuddy's Crag and Housesteads Crag CC BY-SA 2.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Incidences: sites; potters; n

Assumed Dated Sites in Britannia in a CA

$$f(x) = \frac{(b-a)(x - \min)}{\max - \min} + a$$

Normalising CA 1st Dimension values and converting into gradient colours using rainbow.js


```

1 "id"|"site"|"lon"|"lat"|"x"|"y"|"norm"|"hex"
2 "1001570"|"Camulodunum"|"0.899999"|"51.883335"|" -2.4689"|" -1.7971"|"0"|"#310769"
3 "1003148"|"Maidstone"|"0.51667"|"51.26667"|" -1.2852"|" -0.0088"|"28.015241882"|"#234c92"
4 "1003533"|"Fingringhoe Wick"|"0.969736"|"51.83586"|" -1.1808"|" -0.2368"|"30.486130834"|"#225396"
5 "1001198"|"Wimborne"|" -2.014188"|"50.79"|" -1.0293"|"0.0269"|"34.0717599167"|"#205b9b"
6 "1003475"|"Mancetter"|" -1.518985"|"52.566791"|" -0.9793"|"0.0567"|"35.2551358516"|"#205e9c"
7 "1002701"|"Braughing"|"0.02789"|"51.90684"|" -0.6397"|" -0.3673"|"43.2926252012"|"#1c72a8"
8 "1001765"|"Usk"|" -2.9"|"51.7"|" -0.5209"|"0.7939"|"46.1043264224"|"#1a79ac"
9 "1002137"|"Great Chesterford"|"0.2"|"52.066665"|" -0.5170"|" -0.3360"|"46.1966297453"|"#1a7aac"
10 "1001387"|"Baldock"|" -0.18835"|"51.98781"|" -0.4988"|"0.2398"|"46.6273785856"|"#1a7bad"
11 "1000900"|"Worcester"|" -2.2"|"52.2"|" -0.4403"|"0.2798"|"48.0119284294"|"#197eaf"
12 "1001979"|"Silchester"|" -1.10061"|"51.35356"|" -0.4292"|" -0.2287"|"48.274637887"|"#197faf"
13 "1003975"|"Old Winteringham"|" -0.596903"|"53.688995"|" -0.4212"|"0.4536"|"48.4639780365"|"#197fb0"
14 "1000455"|"Baginton"|" -1.483333"|"52.366664"|" -0.3792"|"0.8311"|"49.4580138218"|"#1982b1"
15 "1002961"|"Wall"|" -1.866933"|"52.656707"|" -0.3721"|"0.4928"|"49.6260532046"|"#1982b1"
16 "1001839"|"Exeter"|" -3.52751"|"50.7236"|" -0.3446"|"0.5101"|"50.2769099688"|"#1884b2"
17 "1003671"|"Canterbury"|"1.07992"|"51.27904"|" -0.3415"|" -0.1198"|"50.3502792767"|"#1884b3"
18 "1003799"|"Northchurch"|" -0.599707"|"51.775375"|" -0.3399"|"1.0421"|"50.3881473066"|"#1884b3"
19 "1000080"|"Colchester"|"0.899999"|"51.883338"|" -0.2860"|"0.0771"|"51.6638265644"|"#1887b4"
20 "1002343"|"Fishbourne"|" -0.810943"|"50.839269"|" -0.2636"|"0.1874"|"52.1939789832"|"#1788b5"
21 "1001331"|"Arlesey"|" -0.2654"|"52.007"|" -0.2459"|"1.3322"|"52.6128940642"|"#1789b6"
22 "1003862"|"Southwark"|" -0.089161"|"51.5"|" -0.1645"|"0.2654"|"54.5394300861"|"#168eb9"
23 "1001888"|"Chelmsford"|"0.483333"|"51.733329"|" -0.1637"|"0.2880"|"54.5583641011"|"#168eb9"
24 "1000969"|"Chichester"|" -0.783333"|"50.833328"|" -0.1320"|"0.1205"|"55.3086244438"|"#1690ba"
25 "1003699"|"Sandy"|" -0.283333"|"52.116664"|" -0.1270"|"0.3607"|"55.4269620373"|"#1690ba"
26 "1003896"|"Alcester"|" -1.866667"|"52.21667"|" -0.1076"|"0.2755"|"55.8861119"|"#1692bb"
27 "1001764"|"Cirencester"|" -1.983332"|"51.733329"|" -0.0880"|"0.1354"|"56.3499952665"|"#1593bb"
28 "1004100"|"Southampton"|" -1.40428"|"50.90395"|" -0.0639"|"0.7601"|"56.9203824671"|"#1594bc"
29 "1001046"|"Richborough"|"1.333333"|"51.283329"|" -0.0580"|"0.0367"|"57.0600208274"|"#1595bc"
30 "1004140"|"Bath"|" -2.357391"|"51.381506"|" -0.0300"|"0.2659"|"57.7227113509"|"#1596bd"
31 "1002885"|"Caerhûn"|" -3.833333"|"53.216667"|" -0.0263"|"0.1363"|"57.8102811701"|"#1596bd"
32 "1000136"|"London"|" -0.09184"|"51.51279"|" -0.0207"|"0.1535"|"57.9428192748"|"#1597be"
33 "1000375"|"Lincoln"|" -0.533333"|"53.233333"|" -0.0199"|"0.2723"|"57.9617532898"|"#1597be"

```


FAIRification with RDF and Linked Open Data

```

1 "id"|"site"|"lon"|"lat"|"x"|"y"|"norm"|"hex"
2 "1001570"|"Camulodunum"|"0.899999"|"51.883335"|"2.4689"|"1.7971"|"0"|"#310769"
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4 "1003533"|"Fingringhoe Wick"|"0.969736"|"51.83586"|"1.1808"|"0.2368"|"30.486130834"|"#225396"
5 "1001198"|"Wimborne"|"2.014188"|"50.79"|"1.0293"|"0.0269"|"34.0717599167"|"#205b9b"
6 "1003475"|"Mancetter"|"1.518985"|"52.566791"|"0.9793"|"0.0567"|"35.2551358516"|"#205e9c"
7 "1002701"|"Braughing"|"0.02789"|"51.90684"|"0.6397"|"0.3673"|"43.2926252012"|"#1c72a8"
8 "1001763"|"Usk"|"2.9"|"51.7"|"0.5209"|"0.7939"|"46.3083264224"|"#1a79ae"
9 "1002137"|"Great Chesterford"|"0.2"|"52.066665"|"0.5170"|"0.3360"|"46.1966297453"|"#1a7aac"
10 "1001387"|"Baldock"|"0.18835"|"51.98781"|"0.4988"|"0.2398"|"46.6273785856"|"#1a7bad"
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14 "1000455"|"Baginton"|"1.483333"|"52.366664"|"0.3792"|"0.8311"|"49.4580138218"|"#1982b1"
15 "1002961"|"Wall"|"1.066933"|"52.656707"|"0.3721"|"0.4928"|"49.6268532046"|"#1982b1"
16 "1001830"|"Exeter"|"3.52751"|"50.7236"|"0.3468"|"0.5101"|"50.2769909688"|"#1884b9"
17 "1003671"|"Canterbury"|"1.07992"|"51.27904"|"0.3415"|"0.1198"|"50.3502792767"|"#1884b3"
18 "1003799"|"Northchurch"|"0.599707"|"51.775375"|"0.3399"|"1.0421"|"50.3881473066"|"#1884b3"
19 "1000080"|"Colchester"|"0.899999"|"51.883338"|"0.2860"|"0.0771"|"51.6638265644"|"#1887b4"
20 "1002343"|"Fishbourne"|"0.810943"|"50.839269"|"0.2636"|"0.1874"|"52.1939789832"|"#1780b5"
21 "1001331"|"Arlesey"|"0.2654"|"52.007"|"0.2459"|"1.3322"|"52.6128940642"|"#1789b6"
22 "1003862"|"Southwark"|"0.089161"|"51.5"|"0.1645"|"0.2654"|"54.5394300861"|"#168eb9"
23 "1001888"|"Chelmsford"|"0.483333"|"51.733329"|"0.1637"|"0.2880"|"54.5583641011"|"#168eb9"
24 "1000909"|"Chichester"|"0.783333"|"50.933328"|"0.1308"|"0.1205"|"55.3086244438"|"#1690ba"
25 "1003699"|"Sandy"|"0.283333"|"52.116664"|"0.1270"|"0.3607"|"55.4289620373"|"#1690ba"
26 "1003896"|"Alcester"|"1.866667"|"52.21667"|"0.1076"|"0.2755"|"55.8861119"|"#1692bb"
27 "1001764"|"Cirencester"|"1.983332"|"51.733329"|"0.0880"|"0.1354"|"56.3499952665"|"#1593bb"
28 "1004100"|"Southampton"|"1.40428"|"50.90395"|"0.0639"|"0.7601"|"56.9203824671"|"#1594bc"
29 "1001046"|"Richborough"|"1.333333"|"51.283329"|"0.0580"|"0.0367"|"57.0600208274"|"#1595bc"
30 "1004140"|"Bath"|"2.357391"|"51.381506"|"0.0300"|"0.2659"|"57.7227113509"|"#1596bd"
31 "1002885"|"Caerhün"|"3.833333"|"53.216667"|"0.0263"|"0.1363"|"57.8102811701"|"#1596bd"
32 "1000136"|"London"|"0.09184"|"51.51279"|"0.0207"|"0.1535"|"57.9428192748"|"#1597be"
33 "1000375"|"Lincoln"|"0.533333"|"53.233333"|"0.0199"|"0.2723"|"57.9617532898"|"#1597be"

```

```

# read csv file
data = pd.read_csv(
    file_in,
    encoding='utf-8',
    sep='|',
    usecols=['id', 'site', 'lon', 'lat', 'x', 'y', 'norm', 'hex'],
    na_values=['.', '??', 'NULL'] # take any '.' or '??' values as NA
)
print(data.info())

# create triples from dataframe
lineNo = 2
outStr = ""
lines = []
ids = []
for index, row in data.iterrows():
    # print(lineNo)
    tmpno = lineNo - 2
    if tmpno % 1000 == 0:
        print(tmpno)
    lineNo += 1

# site metadata
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " +
            str(row['id']) + " " + "rdf:type" + " lado:Location .")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " +
            str(row['id']) + " " + "rdf:type" + " lado:DiscoverySite .")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " +
            str(row['id']) + " " + "rdf:type" + " lado:ToGeR_Event .")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " +
            str(row['id']) + " " + "lado:hasType" + " lado:DiscoverySite .")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " " + "rdfs:label" +
            " " + " " + str(row['site']).replace('\\', '\\\\') + "@en" + ".")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " " + " " +
            "dc:identifier" + " " + " " + str(row['id']) + " " + ".")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " " + "lado:tiger_eventname" +
            " " + " " + str(row['site']).replace('\\', '\\\\') + "@en" + ".")
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " " + " " +
            "lado:tiger_id" + " " + " " + str(row['id']) + " " + ".")
ids.append(str(row['id']))

# geom
point = "POINT(" + str(float(row['lat'])) + \
        " " + str(float(row['lon'])) + ")"
point = "\<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> " + \
        point + "\^^geosparql:wktLiteral"
lines.append("samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " " + " " +
            "geosparql:hasGeometry" + " samian:loc_ds " + str(row['id']) + " _geom .")

```


Using Research Software to transform the data

created by <https://www.ldf.fi/service/rdf-grapher>

Londinium and its temporal neighbours as RDF

Goscinny, Uderzo. 2004. Asterix in Britain, No. VIII, pp. 5

Londinium and its temporal neighbours on a Map

sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc Public

main 1 branch 0 tags

Go to file Add file Code

About

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

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situx Timo florianthieri Florian Thiery

Commit history:

Commit	Message	Time
situx update		10 minutes ago
.github/workflows	Update udoc.yml	2 days ago
resources/html	updates js libs	yesterday
LICENSE	Initial commit	2 years ago
README.md	Update README.md	2 months ago
docgeneration.py	update	10 minutes ago
prefixes.json	Add files via upload	6 months ago

README.md

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

This repository hosts a standalone version of the HTML documentation feature included in the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Rather than initiating the documentation generation within the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin, this python script allows the generation of the documentation standalone or as a Github Action.

The standalone script does not rely on QGIS classes and does not provide the full functionality available in the SPARQL Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Deviations from the SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin are listed as follows:

- Support for less geometry literals: Only WKT and GeoJSON literals are supported for rendering

Usage Example

For a usage example please refer to this repository: https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS_testdata

img via <https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc>

The SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation can act as a HTML Page generator in GitHub Actions.

DiscoverySite Instances Collection EN

http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/DiscoverySite_collection

The DiscoverySite Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Download Options: Format:

Property	Value
type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection)
label (rdfs:label)	DiscoverySite Instances Collection (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
member (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ 155 values ■ Aislingen (samianloc_ds_1000815) ■ Alcester (samianloc_ds_1003896) ■ Alchester (samianloc_ds_1003810) ■ Andernach (samianloc_ds_1001308) ■ Arlesey (samianloc_ds_1001331) ■ Arnsburg (samianloc_ds_1000983) ■ Augsburg (samianloc_ds_1003165) ■ Bad Cannstatt (samianloc_ds_1000346) ■ Baden-Baden (samianloc_ds_1002130) ■ Bæinton (samianloc_ds_1000455)

images via https://leiza-rse.github.io/tiger/DiscoverySite_collection/index.html

GeoClasses:

Search:

- Activity (prov:Activity) [155]
- Collection (skos:Collection) [1]
- SpatialObjectCollection (gsp:SpatialObjectCollection)
- FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection) [3]
 - DiscoverySite Instances Collection (samian:DiscoverySite_)
 - Location Instances Collection (samian:Location_collection)
 - TiGeR_Event Instances Collection (samian:TiGeR_Event_c)
- GeometryCollection (gsp:GeometryCollection) [1]
- DiscoverySite (lado:DiscoverySite) [155]
- Location (lado:Location) [155]
- Point (sf:Point) [155]
- TiGeR_Event (lado:TiGeR_Event) [155]

All TiGeR-Discovery Sites as a Feature Collection

Londinium^{EV}

http://data.archaeology.link/data/samian/loc_ds_1000136

The Londinium resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: **Turtle (TTL)** Download

Property	Value
hasType (lado:hasType)	DiscoverySite (lado:DiscoverySite)
tiger_cax (lado:tiger_cax)	-0.0207 (xmils:decimal)
tiger_cax_hex (lado:tiger_cax_hex)	#1597be (xsd:string)
tiger_cax_norm (lado:tiger_cax_norm)	0.57943 (xmils:decimal)
tiger_cay (lado:tiger_cay)	0.1535 (xmils:decimal)
tiger_eventname (lado:tiger_eventname)	Londinium (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
tiger_id (lado:tiger_id)	1000136 (xmils:integer)
hasGeometry (gsp:hasGeometry)	loc_ds_1000136_geom (samian:loc_ds_1000136_geom)
type (rdf:type)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DiscoverySite (lado:DiscoverySite) Location (lado:Location) TiGeR_Event (lado:TiGeR_Event)
label (rdfs:label)	Londinium (rdf:langString) (iso6391:en)
intervalBefore (time:intervalBefore)	Lincoln (samian:loc_ds_1000375)
is member (rdfs:member) of	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DiscoverySite Instances Collection (samian:DiscoverySite_collection) Location Instances Collection (samian:Location_collection) TiGeR_Event Instances Collection (samian:TiGeR_Event_collection)

The Londinium TiGeR-result as LOD HTML Page

via <https://leiza-rse.solidweb.org/tiger/CA2MapBritannia.ttl>

```
1 SELECT ?item ?lat ?geo ?colour WHERE {
2 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://archaeology.link/ontology#TiGeR_Event> .
3 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
4 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
5 ?item <http://archaeology.link/ontology#tiger_cax_norm> ?colour .
6 }
```


LOD stored in a Solid Pod and queried via the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin with gradient colours

Item Discussion

Londinium (Q927198)

settlement established on the current site of the City of London around AD 43

Roman London

↕ In more languages

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Londinium	settlement established on the current site of the City of London around AD 43	Roman London
German	Londinium	Hauptstadt der römischen Provinz Britannien, das heutige London	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
Polish	Londinium	No description defined	

<http://wikidata.org/entity/Q927198>

Item Discussion

Asterix in Britain (Q677479)

comic book album

↕ In more languages

Language	Label	Description
English	Asterix in Britain	comic book album
German	Asterix bei den Briten	Asterix-Album
American English	No label defined	No description defined
Polish	Asteriks u Brytów	No description defined

<http://wikidata.org/entity/Q677479>

Goscinny, Uderzo. 2004. Asterix in Britain, No. VIII, pp. 5-6

... and related to Asterix Comics :-)

Use Case II: Limes Sections

CA to a virtual timeline & RDF graphs

Alligator FAIRification Research Tool

The Alligator Method

The Alligator Algorithm starts with 3D distance calculations using the coordinates of the first 3 CA dimensions.

based on <https://github.com/RGZM/alligator>

- ... some Limes parts have a terminus post quem point (derived from a historical source)
- ... some Limes parts have a terminus ante quem point (derived from dendro dates)
- ... some Limes parts have no datings and are floating between other fixed parts

Then the Alligator Algorithm calculates undated wobbly floating periods by finding the next 3D CA neighbour.

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Following this, the new virtual time intervals are calculated and the resulting virtual fuzzy years are generated based on Allen's Interval Algebra.

name	x	y	z	von	bis	fixed
AlbLimes	-0.226	0.109	-0.514	97	260	fixed
DonauLimesPhase1	-0.884	-0.224	0.256	30	70	fixed
DonauLimesPhase2	-0.216	-0.188	-0.139	70	260	fixed
Elisabethenstrasse	0.029	0.397	-0.085	74	104	fixed
HardriansWall	0.786	-0.558	-0.915	?	?	<i>floating</i>
Neckarlimes	0.080	-0.725	0.389	117	260	fixed
NoordzeeKust	0.625	0.561	1.304	120	?	<i>floating</i>
Wetteraulimes	0.649	-0.289	0.038	110	260	fixed

The Alligator calculates vague floating intervals for Limes sections: Hadrian's Wall and the North Sea Coast.

The process of nearest neighbour findings suggests a starting date of Hadrian's Wall similar to Wetterau Limes.

name	x	y	z	von	bis	fixed
AlbLimes	-0.226	0.109	-0.514	97	260	fixed
DonauLimesPhase1	-0.884	-0.224	0.256	30	70	fixed
DonauLimesPhase2	-0.216	-0.188	-0.139	70	260	fixed
Elisabethenstrasse	0.029	0.397	-0.085	74	104	fixed
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NoordzeeKust	0.625	0.561	1.304	120	260	<i>floating</i>
Wetteraulimes	0.649	-0.289	0.038	110	260	fixed

The calculated virtual fuzzy years seem to confirm the widespread assumption that Hadrian's Wall, the North Sea Coast foundations and the Wetterau Limes were founded in the same decades.

Based on very similar Samian consumption profiles, Hadrian's Wall, the North Sea Coast and Wetterau-Limes are all located on the right (late) side.

created with <https://www.ldf.fi/service/rdf-grapher>

Hadrian's Wall and the Alligator calculations as RDF

Hadrian's Wall and the Allen Intervals as RDF

Conclusio & Outlook

Although it is very well possible with Samian as a find category to establish relative chronologies, it has a less reliable capability for yielding absolute dates.

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However, Do we need a different concept of temporalities for such dated sites?

**Wobbling datings due to
varying underlying production cycles**

Thank you for your attention.

Questions?

